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Linear Combination of Road Network Indices and their Spatial Nature: A Statistical Approach for Connectivity Analysis of Rural District.

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ABSTRACT:

The transport network system is crucial to the growth of any region. Therefore, the road network is regarded as essential to regional growth yet. This article uses a variety of indices, including the ATA (Aggregate Transport Score), cyclomatic number, beta, gamma, eta, and alpha indices to analyze the road network connectivity of the Purba Medinipur district in West Bengal. The results reveal that, the block with the highest ATS score was Bhagwanpur-II, while the block with the lowest score was Patashpur-I. Calculating weight values allows one to assess the efficiency % of various indices. Lastly, statistical techniques were used to measure the Road Network Density (RND) and Grid Tree pattern (GTP), which are stated in methodology section. In accordance to the GTP, eight blocks are in the grid pattern and the remaining seventeen are in the tree pattern. In the entire district, the Bhagwanpur-II block has the highest road network density then the other considered blocks. Through the use of these tools, any regional imbalance may be evaluated, created or not, which aids in the development of plans and actions for it.

Keywords: Transport network, regional development, connectivity, Road Network Density.

Introduction:

One of the four conventional components of economic geography is transportation, together with primary production, manufacturing, marketing, and transportation. In the past, transportation was studied as a component of the economy; but, as knowledge in other fields, such as geography, has grown, transportation geography has become a separate subject of study, and over the past 50 years, many geographers have contributed significantly to it. A subfield of combinatorial topology called graph theory offers useful instruments for measuring and analyzing the structural aspects of transportation networks (Raza and Aggarwal, 1986).

A transport network is a collection of links that indicate connections between locations. Graph theory and network analysis can be used to assess the effectiveness of these networks by determining the number of links between points and the associated revenues from traffic flows. (Rodrigue, 2020). A graph is a symbolic representation of a network and its connection in transport geography, similar to an abstraction of reality reduced to a set of connected nodes. Networks are examined for connectivity. Transport geography differs from other areas of the subject that are more focused on points or areas in that it studies the structural analysis of networks and the patterns that these networks have produced. As a result, the transport links themselves can be seen as networks that can be analysed to measure accessibility (Knowles and Wareing, 2014). Transport networks play a crucial part in the overall development of the region by linking geographical locations that are connected to one another through several linked routes (Kansky, 1963).

In addition to being a vital means of existence, transportation plays a remarkable role in society. It deals with the flow of people and things as well as the more general concepts of ideas, politics, money, and credit (Hurst, 1973; Dostal and Adamec, 2011). In addition to being a crucial part of the economy and sustaining the physical relationships between locales, transportation facilities and modes have played a significant role in the evolution of human activities around the world (Hall et al., 2006). One crucial factor that may be examined to evaluate a region's connection and accessibility is the pattern and structure of its transport networks (Knowles and Wareing, 2014). The dynamics of the complex network arrangement and the evolution of transport networks based on nodes and edges properties are the only things that the topology of transport networks alone can provide; it cannot give the full picture of the underlying factors influencing the development of road networks (Ducruet and Lugo, 2013). Numerous significant elements, including terrain and drainage systems, as well as a region's strategic, political, social, and economic significance, have an impact on how a region's transport network develops (Sarkar and Hannan, 2022).

Study Area:

South Bengal's Purba Medinipur, often known as East Medinipur, is a coastline district. On January 1st, 2002, the district was created through the division of the bigger Medinipur district. The Hooghly River and South 24 Parganas district are to the east of this district, the Rupnarayan River and Howrah district to the northeast, and the Bay of Bengal to the south, west, and north encircle this district. The districts headquarter is in Tamluk. The district was situated between latitudes 21° 36' and 22° 57' N and longitudes 86° 33' and 88° 12' E. The district has a total area of 4713 square kilometers and a population of 5,095,875 as of the 2011 census. The population density is approximately 1082 people per square kilometer, with an 87.66 percent literacy rate and a sex ratio of 936 females for every 1000 males. There are twenty-five Community Development Blocks (CDB) in the district. Panskura, Kolaghat, Tamluk, Sahid Matangini, Nandakumar, Mahishadal, Moyna, Potashpur-I, Potashpur-II, Bhagawanpur-II, Bhagawanpur-I, Chandipur, Sutahata, Haldia, Nandigram-I, Nandigram-II, Khejuri-I, Khejuri-II, Contai-I, Deshapran, Contai-III, Egra-I, Egra-II, Ramnagar-I and Ramnagar-II are these blocks.

Figure 1: Location Map of the Study Area

Objectives:

The following lists this paper's primary goals: 1. To examine the blocks' road network connectedness using a variety of network indices, including ATS, cyclomatic number, beta, gamma, and eta. 2. To determine the percentage of efficiency and weights assigned to various indicators. 3. To determine the study area's block-by-block road density and GTP.

Materials and Methodology:

In transportation studies, the use of GIS is a valuable source for data calibration. Secondary sources of data have been used in this study and processed in GIS techniques. Required information gathered for this study from the Department of Rural Development, Ministry of India, 2022. <https://geosadak-pmgsy.nic.in/opendata/> is the website for the PMGSY (Pradhan Mantri Gram Sadak Yojana) National GIS Rural Connectivity Datasets. The main Purba Medinipur roads served as the basis for our investigation. district shape file, block by block, gathered from mapgis.in. For the statistical analysis and mapping produced using ArcGIS 10.6 and MS Excel 2016. The next section discusses a detail of the techniques utilized in this paper: The most widely used statistic for measuring road network connectivity is the alpha index (α). The Alpha index has values between 0 and 1. Minimum connectivity is represented by the number 0, and maximum connectivity is represented by the number 1. Here, the connectivity relationship between the Alpha Index, Beta Index (β), Gamma Index (γ), and Eta Index (η) is induced by edge (e) and node (v) using the following equations:

$$\text{Alpha Index}(\alpha) = \frac{e-v+1}{2v-5} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Beta Index}(\beta) = \frac{e}{v} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Gamma Index}(\gamma) = \frac{e}{3(v-2)} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Eta Index}(\eta) = \frac{\text{Total network distance}}{\text{number of arcs}} \quad (4)$$

Cyclomatic Number(μ) is also an important measure of road network connectivity. Higher value of Cyclomatic number reflects a higher degree of connectivity. It is calculated as:

$$\text{Cyclomatic number}(\mu) = e - v + p \quad (5)$$

The overall value of each block's cyclomatic number, beta index, gamma index, eta index, and alpha index is known as the aggregate transport score, or ATS. The ATS value is calculated using the formula below:

$$\text{Aggregate Transport Score}(ATS) = \alpha + \beta + \gamma + \eta + \mu \quad (6)$$

The corresponding coefficients (Weights) of the indices are computed when the estimated indicators are accumulated in a linear fashion using the Shannon Entropy (Shannon, 1948) (Mitra et al., 2021). All five of the indices have had their weightage values determined using the Shannon Entropy algorithm below:

$$P_{ij} = \frac{x_{ij}}{\sum_{i=1}^m x_{ij}} \quad (7)$$

Where, m represents the number of blocks and P_{ij} is the proportional occurrence of the value x_{ij} corresponds to j^{th} evaluated parameter (index) in i^{th} sample (block), calculated by using the following formula:

$$E_j = -k \sum_{i=1}^m P_{ij} \ln P_{ij} \quad (8)$$

Where, K is the proportionality constant and measured as

$$k = \frac{1}{\ln(m)}$$

Corresponding weight of the j^{th} parameter (index), denoted by W_j , for $j=1,2,3,\dots$ is evaluated as:

$$W_j = \frac{1-E_j}{\sum_{j=1}^n (1-E_j)} \quad (9)$$

The road network pattern can also be divided using the GTP(Grid Tree Pattern) Index. It can be evaluated in three different ways: as a tree pattern, grid pattern, or delta pattern, with corresponding index values ranging from 0 to 0.5, 0.5 to 1.0, and 1.0 to 2.0. The following formula is used to compute it:

$$\text{GTP Index} = \frac{e-v+p}{(\sqrt{v}-1)^2} \quad (10)$$

The primary driving force behind density analysis is the rational layout of the entire road's length and area. The following formula can be used to quantify that:

$$\text{Density of Road Network}(DRN) = \frac{\text{Length of the road}(km)}{\text{Area}(sq.km)} \quad (11)$$

Results and discussion:

With the aid of the ArcGIS 10.6 software version, we were able to identify the block-wise nodes and edges (Figures 2 and 3) of the entire district prior to methodological application. Then, a number of methodological procedures were used. Here, Table 1 shows Purba Medinipur's Road Network Connectivity Summary of this study.

Figure 2: Road Network of the Study Area

Figure 3: Nodes and Edge of the Study Area

Table 1: Summary of Road Network Connectivity of Purba Medinipur

BLOCK	Node (v)	Edge (e)	α	β	γ	μ	η	ATS	GTP	DRN
Bhagwanpur-I	158	212	0.17	1.34	0.45	53	1.17	56.13	0.40	1.33
Bhagwanpur-II	481	641	0.17	1.33	0.45	159	0.64	161.59	0.36	2.25
Chandipur	135	209	0.28	1.55	0.52	73	0.99	76.34	0.65	1.51
Contai-I	163	219	0.17	1.34	0.45	55	1.23	58.19	0.40	1.61
Contai-III	134	190	0.21	1.42	0.48	55	1.29	58.39	0.49	1.52
Deshpran	174	225	0.15	1.29	0.44	50	1.13	53.01	0.34	1.49
Egra-I	212	260	0.11	1.23	0.41	47	1.09	49.84	0.26	1.28
Egra-II	235	305	0.15	1.30	0.44	69	0.93	71.81	0.34	1.51
Haldia	88	125	0.21	1.42	0.48	36	0.93	39.05	0.51	0.70
Khejuri-I	119	164	0.19	1.38	0.47	44	1.11	47.15	0.45	1.50
Khejuri-II	79	100	0.13	1.27	0.43	20	1.64	23.47	0.32	1.21
Kolaghat	86	99	0.07	1.15	0.39	12	1.68	15.29	0.18	1.10
Mahishadal	89	128	0.22	1.44	0.49	38	1.50	41.65	0.53	1.50
Moyna	86	108	0.13	1.26	0.43	21	1.69	24.50	0.31	1.20
Nandakumar	144	216	0.25	1.50	0.51	71	1.04	74.29	0.59	1.39
Nandigram-I	99	148	0.25	1.49	0.51	48	1.44	51.69	0.60	1.29
Nandigram-II	71	93	0.15	1.31	0.45	21	1.60	24.51	0.38	1.41
Panskura	203	230	0.06	1.13	0.38	26	1.54	29.12	0.15	1.44

BLOCK	Node (v)	Edge (e)	α	β	γ	μ	η	ATS	GTP	DRN
Patashpur-I	228	239	0.02	1.05	0.35	10	0.99	12.41	0.05	1.36
Patashpur-II	226	287	0.13	1.27	0.43	60	0.98	62.81	0.30	1.45
Ramnagar-I	228	249	0.04	1.09	0.37	20	0.88	22.38	0.10	1.67
Ramnagar-II	219	291	0.16	1.33	0.45	71	0.91	73.85	0.37	1.65
Sahid Matangini	89	143	0.31	1.61	0.55	53	1.05	56.51	0.75	1.67
Sutahata	72	102	0.21	1.42	0.49	29	1.18	32.29	0.52	1.58
Tamluk	106	157	0.24	1.48	0.50	50	1.09	53.31	0.58	1.32

Source: Computed by authors

In the research on planar networks, the alpha index (α) is also referred to as the meshing coefficient (Ducruet et al., 2013). Kolaghat, Panskura, Patashpur-I, Egra-I, and Ramnagar-I blocks are located in the Low (0.02-0.12) value region; Moyna, Bhagwanpur-I, Bhagwanpur-II, Patashpur-II, Egra-II, Ramnagar-II, Contai-I, Contai-III, Deshapran, Khejuri-I, Khejuri-II, Nandigram-II, Sutahata, and Haldia blocks are located in the Moderate (0.13-0.21) value region; Sahid Matangini, Tamluk, Nandakumar, Mahishhadal, Chandipur, and Nandigram-I are situated in the High (0.22-0.31) value region. As per follows the Alpha Index 56 % of blocks considered as moderate, 24 % are lying between high region and 20 % specified as low values over the district. Additionally, the blocks with high alpha values were clustered eaatern side of the district, while the blocks with medium alpha values were associated in the central section of the district, and having low-value blocks were apartly located along the northern and western edges of the district. (Table -2 and Figure -4). Noticeably, Sahid Matangini block having ranks highest (0.31) and followed by Chandipur (0.28), Nandakumar (0.25), Nandigram-I (0.25), and Tamluk (0.24) blocks respectively. On the other hand, Patashpur-I (0.02) block exist lowest rank in term of Alpha Index calculation followed by Ramnagar-I (0.04), Panskura (0.06), Kolaghat (0.07) and Egra-I (0.11) blocks respectively (Table-1).

Table 2: Block-wise Alpha Index Value

Alpha Index Value	Name of the Blocks	No. of Blocks	% of Block
Low (0.02- 0.12)	Kolaghat, Panskura, Patashpur-I, Egra-I, Ramnagar-I.	5	20
Moderate (0.13-0.21)	Moyna, Bhagwanpur-II, Bhagwanpur-I Patashpur-II, Egra-II, RamnagarII, Contai-I, Contai-III, Deshapran, Khejuri-I, Khejuri-II, Nandigram-II, Sutahata, Haldia.	14	56
High (0.22-0.31)	Sahid Matangini, Tamluk, Nandakumar, Mahishadal, Chandipur, Nandigram-I.	6	24

Figure 4: Block -wise Alpha (α) Index

Source: Computed by authors

The Beta Index (β) can be seen as the average number of linkages that lead into or out of each node because it reflects the number of edges existing in relation to the number of vertices that need to be connected. The period with the highest value denotes the one with maximum connectivity when the average of each is taken into account, and the period with the lowest value shows the least connected. (Abbas and colleagues, 2019) The beta index value is shown in Table 3 and Figure 5. The following blocks are located in low (1.05–1.24) value: Moyna, Bhagwanpur–I, Bhagwanpur–I, Patashpur–II, Egra–II, Ramnagar–II, Contai–I, Contai–III, Deshapran, Khejuri–I, Khejuri–II, Nandigram–II, Sutahata, and Haldia; in moderate (1.25–1.42) value are Kolaghat, Panskura, Patashpur–I, Egra–I, and Ramnagar–I blocks; and in high (1.43–1.61) value are Sahid Matangini, Tamluk, Nandakumar, Mahishadal, Chandigpur, and Nandigram–I. It was recorded that Sahid Matangini block achieves rank highest (1.61) in term of Beta Index followed by Chandipur (1.55), Nandakumar (1.50), Nandigram (1.49) and Tamluk (1.48). Patashpur-I indicated lowest rank (1.05) followed by Ramnagar-I (1.09), Panskura (1.13), Kolaghat (1.15) respectively (Table-1).

Table 3: Block-wise Beta Index (β) Value

Beta Index Value	Name of the Blocks	No. of Blocks	% of Block
Low (1.05- 1.24)	Kolaghat, Panskura, Patashpur-I, Egra-I, Ramnagar-I.	5	20
Moderate (1.25-1.42)	Moyna, Bhagwanpur-II, Bhagwanpur-I, Patashpur-II, Egra-II, RamnagarII, Contai-I, Contai-III, Deshapran, Khejuri-I, Khejuri-II, Nandigram-II, Sutahata, Haldia.	14	56

High (1.43-1.61)	Sahid Matangini, Tamluk, Nandakumar,	6	24
	Mahishadal,		
	Chandipur,		
	Nandigram-I.		

Figure 5: Block-wise Beta(β) Index

Source: Computed by authors

The ratio of a network's edges to the maximum number of vertices that can exist between a given number of vertices is known as the gamma index (γ). The expression's denominator captures the notion that adding a vertex inevitably results in an increase of three potential edges. When comparing different time periods, the network with the highest % represents the quantity with the highest level of connectivity, while the network with the lowest percentage represents the least amount of connectivity (Abbas et al., 2019). Five blocks—Kolaghat, Panskura, Patashpur-I, Egra-I, and Ramnagar-I—are shown to be in the low gamma index region in Table 4 and Figure 6. On the other side, the moderate gamma index zone includes 13 blocks: Moyna, Bhagwanpur-I, Bhagwanpur-II, Patashpur-II, Egra-II, Ramnagar-II, Contai-I, Contai-III, Deshapran, Khejuri-I, Khejuri-II, Nandigram-II, and Haldia. The remaining seven blocks, which are in the high gamma index region, are Sahid Matangini, Tamluk, Nandakumar, Mahishadal, Chandipur, Nandigram-I, and Sutaahata. Sahid Matangini block rank highest (0.55), followed by Chandipur (0.52), Nandigram-I (0.51), Nandakumar (0.51) and Tamluk (0.50) respectively. On the other hand, Patashpur-I (0.35) block holds lowest rank in term of Gamma Index followed by Ramnagar-I (0.37), Panskura (0.38) and Kolaghat (0.39) respectively (Table-1).

Table 4: Block- wise Gamma(γ) Index value

Gamma Index Value	Name of the Blocks	No. of Blocks	% of Block
Low (0.35- 0.42)	Kolaghat, Panskura, Patashpur-I, Egra-I, Ramnagar-I.	5	20
Moderate (0.43-0.48)	Moyna, Bhagwanpur-I, Bhagwanpur-II, Patashpur-II, Egra-II, Contai-I,Ramnagar-II, Contai-I,Contai-III, Deshapran, Khejuri-I,Khejuri-II,Nandigram-II, Haldia.	13	52
High (0.49-0.55)	Sahid Matangini, Tamluk, Nandakumar, Mahishadal, Chandipur, Nandigram-I, Sutahata.	7	28

Figure 6: Block -wise Gamma(γ) Index

Source: Computed by authors

As the average length per link decreases, the addition of new nodes will result in a fall in the eta index. Block-wise eta(η) index values are shown in Table 5 and Figure 7. The eight blocks shown in this table are located in the low eta index zone and are named Chandipur, Haldia, Bhagwanpur-II, Patashpur-I, Patashpur-II, Egra-II, Ramnagar-I, and Ramnagar-II. The ten blocks in the moderate eta index zone, on the other hand, are Sahid Matangini, Tamluk, Nandakumar, Sutahata, Bhagwanpur-I, Khejuri-I, Contai-I, Deshapran, Contai -III, and Egra-I. Once more, there are seven blocks in the high eta index region: Kolaghat, Panskura, Moyna, Mahishadal, Nandigram-I, Nandigram-II, and Khejuri-II. 40 percent of the blocks in the whole district are addressed moderate, 32 percent are low, and 28 percent are high in respect of Eta index(η) value. Blocks with high eta index values are located in the northwest and east, low eta index values follows north-east and southern area, and blocks with moderate index values are significantly scattered in manner. Furthermore, Moyna block ranked highest (1.69) followed by Kolaghat (1.68), Khejuri-II (1.64) respectively. Bhagwanpur-II ranked lowest (0.64) followed by Ramnagar-I (0.88), Ramnagar-II (0.91), Haldia (0.93), Egra- II(0.93) respectively (Table-1), those are comparatively reflects variable efforts of considered parameters in this study

Table 5: Block-wise Eta Index(η) value

Eta Index Value	Name of the Blocks	No. of Blocks	% of Block
Low (0.64- 0.99)	Chandipur, Haldia, Bhagwanpur-II, Patashpur-I, Patashpur-II, Egra-II, Ramnagar-I, Ramnagar –II.	8	32
Moderate (1.00-1.34)	Sahid Matangini, Tamluk, Nandakumar, Sutahata, Bhagwanpur-I, Khejuri-I, Contai-I, Deshapran, Contai – III, Egra-I	10	40
High (1.35- 1.69)	Kolaghat, Panskura, Moyna, Mahishadal, Nandigram-I, Nandigram-II, Khejuri-II.	7	28

Figure 7: Block-wise Eta Index(η)

Source: Computed by authors

Thus, the basis of cyclomatic number (μ) is the idea that circuits will grow from extra arcs in a network once there are sufficient links or arcs to form a tree. A tree-type graph is indicated by a cyclomatic number of 0, but the cyclomatic number increases as the graph approaches the fully linked district. This method's drawback is that networks with drastically dissimilar shapes could share a cyclomatic number (Waugh, 1995). Nineteen blocks—Kolaghat, Panskura, Patashpur-I, Egra-I, Ramnagar-I, Sahid Matangini, Tamluk, Mahahishadal, Nandigram-I, Sutahata, Moyna, Bhagwanpur-I, Deshapran, Khejuri-I, Khejuri-II, Nandigram-II, and Haldia—belong to the low cyclomatic number value. Table 6 and Figure 8 illustrate this. Once more, the moderate cyclomatic index zone includes five blocks: Chandipur, Nandikur, Patashpur-II, Egra-II, and Ramnagar-II. Only Bhagwanpur-II block belong to high cyclomatic number value. The block with high cyclomatic number is plotted in the central section of the district, the blocks with moderate cyclomatic number are located in the north-east corner and south-west corner of the district. It is established that, low cyclomatic number is significant for this analysis, which reveals the rank denomination of the study area. The result show that, Bhagwanpur-II block ranked highest (159) followed by Chandipur (73), Ramnagar-II (71), Egra-II (69) respectively. Let it is also established that, Patashpur-II ranked lowest (10) followed by Kolaghat (12), Ramnagar-I (20), Moyna (21) respectively (Table-1).

Table 6: Block-wise Cyclomatic number(μ) value

Cyclomatic number Value	Name of the Blocks	No. of Blocks	% of Block
Low (10- 60)	Kolaghat, Panskura, Patashpur-I,Egra-I,Ramnagar-I, Sahid Matangini, Tamluk, Mahishadal, Nandigram-I, Sutahata,Moyna, Bhagwanpur-I, Contai-I,Contai-III,Deshapran, Khejuri-I, Khejuri-II,Nandigram-II, Haldia.	19	76
Moderate (61- 109)	Chandipur, Nandakumar, Patashpur-II, Egra-II, Ramnagar-II	5	20
High (110-159)	Bhagwanpur-II	1	4

Figure 8: Block-wise Cyclomatic number(μ) value

Source: Computed by authors

Numerous academicians have examined the ATS scores, measuring and analyzing the transport network's accessibility and connection using connectivity indices (Sarkar, 2013). It is evident that the following blocks have nearly equal and lower levels of connectivity: 12.41 to 62.14 for Haldia, Patashpur-I, Ramnagar-I, Sahid Matangini, Tamluk, Sutahata, Bhagwanpur-I, Khejuri-I, Contai-I, Deshapran, Contai –III, Egra-I Kolaghat, Panskura, Moyna, Mahahishadal, Nandigram-I, Nandigram-II, and Khejuri-II. The blocks located in Nandakumar, Chandipur, Patashpur – II, Egra – II, and Ramnagar – II have a marginally enhanced degree of connectedness in contrast to the preceding group. Additionally, Bhagwanpur-II is a block with a high ATS value, resulting in a higher degree of connection (Table 7 and Figure 9). As a result, there aren't many regional differences in the district under study's general connectedness picture. The distribution of the ATS values are quite prominent over the all considered blocks. Thus, it has separately determine the specific gravity of each considered blocks. If we look into this results, it has reveals Low ATS values for 76 percent of blocks, moderate ATS values for 20 percent of blocks, and high ATS values only for rest 4 percent of blocks over the district. Here also, Bhagwanpur-II ranked highest (161.59) followed by Chandipur (76.34), Mahishadal (74.29) respectively. On the other hand, Patashpur-I ranked lowest (12.41) followed by Kolaghat (15.29), Ramnagar-I (22.38) and Khejuri-II (23.47) respectively (Table-1).

Table 7: Block-wise ATS value

ATS Value	Name of the Blocks	No. of Blocks	% of Block
Low (12.41- 62.14)	Haldia, Patashpur-I, Ramnagar-I, Sahid Matangini, Tamluk, Sutahata, Bhagwanpur-I, Khejuri-I, Contai-I, Deshapran, Contai -III, Egra-I Kolaghat, Panskura, Moyna, Mahishadal, Nandigram-I, Nandigram-II, Khejuri-II.	19	76
Moderate (62.15-118.86)	Nandakumar, Chandipur, Patashpur -II, Egra-II, Ramnagar-II.	5	20
High (111.87-161.59)	Bhagwanpur-II,	1	4

Figure 9: Block-wise ATS

Source: Computed by authors

The composite weightage index utilizing Shannon entropy is shown in Table 8, which has been applied here. The following weights are as follows: 0.221759, 0.011976, 0.012574, 0.368965, 0.061264, and 0.323462 for Alpha, Beta, Gamma, Cyclomatic Number, Eta, and ATS. Conversely, it is noted that the efficiency percentages of the various indicators (Alpha, Beta, Gamma, Cyclomatic number, Eta, and ATS) are 22.18, 1.2, 1.26, 36.9, 6.13, and 32.35, respectively.

Table 8: Composite weightage index using Shannon entropy

Indicators	Alpha	Beta	Gamma	C.N	Eta	ATS
Weights(W_j)	0.221759	0.011976	0.012574	0.368965	0.061264	0.323462
Efficiency Percentage	22.18	1.2	1.26	36.9	6.13	32.35

Source: Computed by author

Table- 9 and Figure- 10 shows block-wise GTP. Principle attending the considered GTP, such as Tree or Grid patterns, Moyna, Nandigram-II, Khejuri-II, Bhagwanpur-II, Kolaghat, Panskura, Patashpur-I, Egra-I, Ramnagar-II, Bhagwanpur-I, Khejuri-I, Contai-I, Deshapran, Contai -III falls under Tree pattern. On the other hand, blocks like Sahid Matangini, Tamluk, Nandakumar, Chandipur, Mahishadal, Nandigram-I, Haldia and Sutahata, and Bhagwanpur-II falls under the Grid pattern. The situational configuration of the results direct specified by this analysis. Whereas directional distribution of the pattern is prominent after this analysis, which shown in figure-10.

Table 9: Block-wise GTP (Grid Tree Pattern)

GTP	Name of the Blocks	No. of Blocks	% of Block
Tree Pattern	Patashpur-II, Egra-II, Ramnagar-II, Bhagwanpur-I, Khejuri-I, Contai-I, Deshapran, Contai-III, Moyna, Nandigram-II, Khejuri-II, Bhagwanpur-II, Kolaghat, Panskura, Patashpur-I, Egra-I, Ramnagar-I.	17	68
Grid Pattern	Sahid Matangini, Tamluk, Nandakumar, Chandipur, Mahishadal, Nandigram-I, Haldia, Sutahata.	8	32

Figure 10: Block-wise GTP

Source: Computed by authors

The block-wise road density is shown in both Table 10 and Figure 11, covering Purba Medinipur district. After that, Kolaghat, Moyna, Haldia, and Khejuri-II blocks exhibit low road density. Besides this, Patashpur-I, Egra-I, Ramnagar-I, Bhagwanpur-I, Khejuri-I, Contai-I, Deshapran, Contai -III, Panskura, Patashpur-I, Egra-I, Ramnagar-I, Sahid Matangini, Tamluk, Nandakumar, Chandipur, Mahishadal, Nandigram-I, and Sutahata blocks are conjugately indicates moderate road density coverage. Exceptionally, Bhagwanpur-II block is only with a high road density coverage. The density distribution remarkably indicates high in values in and around the central part of the district. In contrast, maximum blocks (80 percent) are in moderate

road density after this analysis. Overall view of this analysis shows that Bhagwanpur-II block ranked highest (2.25) followed by Ramnagar-I (1.67), Sahid Matangini (1.67), Ramnagar-II (1.65) respectively (Table-1).

Table 10: Block-wise Road density

Road density	Name of the Blocks	No. of Blocks	% of Block
Low (0.77- 1.22)	Kolaghat, Moyna, Haldia, Khejuri-II	4	16
Moderate (1.23- 1.73)	Patashpur-II, Egra-II, Ramnagar-II, Bhagwanpur-I, Khejuri-I, Contai-I, Deshapran, Contai-III, Nandigram-II, Panskura, Patashpur-I, Egra-I, Ramnagar-I, Sahid Matangini, Tamluk, Nandakumar, Chandipur, Mahishadal, Nandigram-I, Sutahata.	20	80
High (1.74-2.25)	Bhagwanpur-II	1	4

Figure 11: Block-wise Road density

Source: Computed by authors

Conclusion:

One of the main factors regulating regional growth is the road network and its spatial pattern and connectivity. This research aims to evaluate the spatial layout and road connectivity throughout Purba Medinipur district in state of West Bengal. In order to measure the differences across 25 blocks, connectivity coverage and spatial pattern are examined here. With the exception of one district town (Tamluk), every block is rural and country roads are used to connect them. District town is solely connected by structural infrastructure via a few highways and one national highway. The methodologies undertaken here are strongly related to each other that explain and satisfy the main objectives of this study. The performances of the considered methods of spatial data are satisfied regarding road density and connectivity analysis. As per the administrative setup of the considered district, Bhagwanpur -II block indicates high density and connectivity in respect of other blocks. Because of that, this block is located almost middle

portion of the district. In reference to considered methods, mainly three subsequent categories are prominent over this district. Transport system and subsequent efforts like land use enhance the semi urban development of the study area. Alpha, Beta, Gamma, Cyclomatic number, Eta and ATS altogether supports to estimate the actual diversity condition related to road network and connectivity. Most southern blocks of this area lies under the less developed in respect of this objectives. Moreover, 4 blocks are less developed, 20 blocks are moderately developed and only Bhagwanpur-II indicates highly developed. This quantitative relationship will provides guidance to undertake any administrative policy for further future development of the entire district.

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Author Contributions

Authors contributed equally to conceptualization, data analysis, and manuscript writing for this study.

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no competing interests (financial or otherwise) to declare.

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Not Applicable.

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Abbreviation

v: Node

e: Edge

α : Alpha Index

β : Beta Index

γ : Gamma Index

μ : Cyclomatic number

η : Eta Index

ATS: Aggregate Transport Score

GTP: Grid Tree Pattern

DRN: Density of Road Network

References:

- (1) Abbas, A. M., and Hashidu, R. B. (2019). Transportation network analysis, connectivity and accessibility indices in North East, Nigeria. *Journal of research in Humanities and Social Science*, 7(9), 60-66.
- (2) Abbas, A. M., and Hashidu, R. B. (2019). Transportation network analysis, connectivity and accessibility indices in North East, Nigeria. *Journal of research in Humanities and Social Science*, 7(9), 60-66.
- (3) Ayo-Odifiri, O. S., Fasakin, J. O., and Henshaw, F. O. (2017). Road connectivity approach to eased traffic congestion on market roads in Benin metropolis, Nigeria. *American Journal of Engineering Research*, 6(6), 41-48.
- (4) Dostál, I., and Adamec, V. (2011). Transport and its Role in the Society. *Transactions on Transport Sciences*, 4(2), 43.
- (5) Ducruet, C., and Lugo, I. (2013). Cities and transport networks in shipping and logistics research. *The Asian Journal of Shipping and Logistics*, 29(2), 145-166.
- (6) Hall, P., Hesse, M., and Jean-Paul, M. (2006). Reexploring the interface between economic and transport geography. *Environment and Planning A*, 38(8), 1401-1408.
- (7) Hurst, M. E. E. (1973). Transportation and the societal framework. *Economic Geography*, 49(2), 163-180.
- (8) Kansky, K. J. (1963). *Structure of transportation networks: relationships between network geometry and regional characteristics*. The University of Chicago.

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- (9) Knowles, R., and Wareing, J. (2014). *Economic and Social geography*. Rupa Publications.(Original work published 1976).
 - (10) Maity, B., Mallick, S. K., and Rudra, S. (2021). Integration of urban expansion with hybrid road transport network development within Haldia Municipality, West Bengal. *The Egyptian Journal of Remote Sensing and Space Science*, 24(3), 471-483.
 - (11) Mitra, S., Hore, S., Roy, S., and Debbarma, D. (2021). Micro-level classification of road network connectivity of Agartala municipal corporation. *Geographical Review of India*,83(3 and 4), 214–234.
 - (12) Raza, M., and Aggarwal, Y. (1986). *Transport geography of India: commodity flows and the regional structure of the Indian economy*. Concept Publishing Company.
 - (13) Rodrigue, J. P., Comtois, C., and Slack, B (2006). *The geography of transport systems (1st ed.)*. Taylor and Francis.
 - (14) Rodrigue, J.-P. (2020). *The geography of transport systems (Fifth Edition)*. Routledge.
 - (15) Sarkar, D. (2013). Structural analysis of existing road networks of Cooch Behar district, West Bengal, India: A transport geographical appraisal. *Ethiopian Journal of Environmental Studies and Management*, 6(1), 74-81.
 - (16) Sarkar, D., and Hannan, A. (2022). Transport System in Pre–Independent Cooch Behar: A Historical Geography Perspective.
 - (17) Sarkar, T., Sarkar, D., and Mondal, P. (2021). Road network accessibility analysis using graph theory and GIS technology: a study of the villages of English Bazar Block, India. *Spatial Information Research*, 29(3), 405-415.
 - (18) Sherpa, K. C., and Hannan, A. (2023). Analysis of rural connectivity and road network development in the Sikkim Himalaya, India. *GeoJournal*, 88(6), 5661-5676.
 - (19) Sreelekha, M. G., Krishnamurthy, K., and Anjaneyulu, M. V. L. R. (2016). Assessment of topological pattern of urban road transport system of Calicut city. *Transportation Research Procedia*, 17, 253-262.
 - (20) Sreelekha, M. G., Krishnamurthy, K., and Anjaneyulu, M. V. L. R. (2020). Urban road network and its topology: case study of Calicut, India. *Eur Transp\Trasporti Europei*, 78.
 - (21) Sreelekha, M. G., Krishnamurthy, K., and Anjaneyulu, M. V. L. R. (2016). Interaction between road network connectivity and spatial pattern. *Procedia technology*, 24, 131-139.
 - (22) Waugh, D. (1995). *Geography- An Integrated Approach* Melbourne: Thomas Nelson and sons Ltd.